

Fabrication of a Single-Pole Double-Throw silicon RF MEMS ohmic contact Switch operating from 50 to 70 GHz

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Abstract — This paper presents a single-pole double-throw (SPDT) RF MEMS ohmic contact switch operating from 50 to 70 GHz. The switch is fabricated using the silicon on glass (SiOG) process. Conventional switches are actuated in one direction (vertical direction), whereas the proposed switch is actuated in two directions (vertical and horizontal directions). By operating two actuators, the switch has high isolation. The RF characteristics are measured from 50 to 70 GHz. The measured insertion loss is more than 20dB before actuation. After the on-state is achieved by the two actuators, the insertion loss is measured and found to be about 10 dB.

I. INTRODUCTION

RF MEMS switches possess several excellent characteristics such as low power consumption, low insertion loss and linearity [1-2]. However, the isolation of an RF MEMS ohmic contact switches at several tens of GHz is low, because of the coupling between the open signal line and the contact part of the switch over the signal line [3-6]. It is a main concern to improve the isolation at high frequencies [7-8]. We propose a silicon RF MEMS ohmic contact switch with high isolation at high frequencies [9]. A single-pole double-throw (SPDT) RF MEMS switch with both horizontal and vertical actuation is presented.

In this paper, we report the fabrication and RF characteristics of a SPDT silicon RF MEMS ohmic contact switch operating from 50 to 70 GHz with high isolation.

II. DESIGN

The contact part of conventional switches structurally is positioned over the signal line directly. This structure causes coupling between the signal line and the contact part of the switch. The proposed RF MEMS switch moves in vertical and lateral directions to improve isolation. The designed switch has a SPDT configuration that consists of a single input port and two output ports. The SPDT RF MEMS switch makes the signal flow through one of the two available output ports. Fig. 1 shows a schematic view of the designed SPDT RF MEMS switch. In other to allow the signal to flow through one of the two output lines, the contact part laterally moves forwards for the on state, or backwards

for the off-state. The lateral motion is created by comb actuators and the vertical motion can be achieved by using a crab leg spring. The two directional motions are activated sequentially.

The switch operation procedure is as follows. First, the contact part is laterally misaligned with respect to the contact area by 30 μm for the off-state of the switch. Second, the contact part is laterally aligned with the contact area by using the comb actuators. When the comb actuator is moved forward, the contact part A of the switch is positioned over the open signal line A, and contact part B is misaligned, creating an off-state for part B. When the comb actuator is moved backward, the contact part B of the switch is positioned over the open signal line B, and the contact part of switch A is misaligned. Third, when the contact part A or B is located over the open signal line, the contact part A or B comes into contact with the open signal line by using crab leg springs for the on-state of the switch.

Fig. 1 Schematic view of the RF MEMS switch

III. FABRICATION

The switch is fabricated using silicon on glass (SiOG) process [10]. The fabrication process is shown in Fig. 2. First, 0.42 μm -thick gold is patterned on a glass wafer with a thickness of 300 μm for the CPW line. The bottom electrodes are patterned on the glass wafer for the vertical actuation. Shallow trenches are patterned on the silicon wafer by DRIE process. The contact part is patterned

inside the shallow trenches and consists of 400 μm -thick aluminium layers, 500 μm -thick silicon dioxide layers and 0.42 μm -thick gold layers. The gold layers are used as the contact metal. The two wafers are then anodically bonded together at 380 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperature and 800 V electrical bias. Chemical mechanical polishing is followed to make the thickness of the silicon wafer go down to 50 μm , after the anodic bonding process. Finally the silicon structure is patterned. DRIE process is followed until the actuators are released and the CPW line is exposed.

Fig. 2 Fabrication process

IV. RESULT

Microphotographs of the fabricated switch are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Microphotographs of the fabricated switch

Fig. 4 shows measured results of the fabricated switch. Only on/off characteristics of switch A is shown. The measurement was performed from 50-70 GHz. The voltage for lateral and vertical actuation is 60 V. The insertion loss of the switch when the contact part is moved over the CPW signal line is decreased compared to the isolation in the off-state in the frequency range from 50-70 GHz. The vertical motion of the contact part produces the on-state of the switch. However, measurement results show that the isolation by sequential

operation doesn't have a clear change. As shown in Fig. 5(a), the results are caused by an impedance mismatch of the CPW line mainly at the corner. As shown in Fig. 5(b), the ground of the CPW line in the areas located near the air-bridges was damaged during the anodic bonding process due to thermal energy.

Fig. 4 Measurement results of the fabricated switch (only switch A is actuating)

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5 (a) Enlarged photograph of switches, (b) Enlarged photograph of air bridge

V. CONCLUSION

The RF MEMS switch is designed to achieve a high isolation between 50-70 GHz at off-state. The switch targets applications requiring a high isolation in the 50-70 GHz range.

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